

Structural breaks in global capture fisheries production (1960–2022): evidence of long-term stabilization

Ivan Zucconelli

Independent Researcher

2026 — Zenodo

Keywords

capture fisheries; time series; structural breaks; Bai–Perron; global production; fisheries statistics; long-term trends

Abstract

This study examines the long-term dynamics of global capture fisheries production over the period 1960–2022 using a structural break approach. Although a global linear regression indicates a positive average trend, this representation tends to obscure important changes in the underlying structure of the series.

The Bai–Perron procedure identifies two breakpoints, in 1972 and 1992, dividing the series into three distinct regimes. An initial phase of rapid expansion is followed by a period of slower growth and, finally, by a phase of substantial stabilization. In the post-1992 period, the estimated trend is weak and not statistically significant, indicating the absence of persistent growth.

The results appear robust and are supported by a substantial reduction in the residual sum of squares in the segmented model compared with the global linear model. Overall, the evidence suggests that global capture fisheries have shifted from a phase of expansion to a long-term plateau.

Introduction

Over the past decades, capture fisheries have increasingly been interpreted as a complex system in which ecological, economic, social, and institutional processes are closely intertwined (Kooiman & Bavinck, 2005; Chuenpagdee et al., 2005). Their global importance is linked not only to food production, but also to their contribution to nutritional security, employment, and livelihoods in many regions of the world (Brander, 2007; Cardinaals et al., 2023).

The literature shows that capture fisheries cannot be assessed solely in terms of catch volumes. The sustainability of the sector also depends on the types of species exploited, fishing areas, harvesting techniques, and ecosystem impacts, all of which tend to be simplified in overly aggregated approaches, including those based on long-term global time series (West et al., 2019). In addition, a substantial share of catches is not directed to human consumption, but instead flows into feed, discards, or other forms of underutilization along the supply chain, thereby reducing the overall nutritional potential of the system (Cardinaals et al., 2023).

A further critical issue concerns the global dimension of supply chains. These often connect distant production areas and consumer markets, making the relationship between final demand and environmental pressures less visible (West et al., 2019). Moreover, the difficulties faced by the sector depend not only on the biological availability of resources, but also on the quality of governance, excess capacity, and the weakness of many regulatory systems (Kooiman & Bavinck, 2005; Chuenpagdee et al., 2005).

This picture is further complicated by the effects of climate change, which operate both gradually, by altering productivity and species distribution, and through extreme events that can affect the safety of fishers, fleets, and habitats (Brander, 2007; Sainsbury et al., 2018). In this context, catch data, despite their limitations, remain a useful tool for identifying long-term trends and possible structural changes in the fisheries system at the global scale (Froese et al., 2012).

On this basis, the present study analyzes the historical series of global capture fisheries production in order to assess whether its long-term trajectory reflects continuous growth or, instead, a succession of distinct structural phases.

To the best of our knowledge, the literature has mainly described the stabilization of global fisheries production in descriptive terms. Explicit analyses of structural breaks applied to the long-term global FAO series remain relatively scarce.

Materials and Methods

The time series analyzed in this study concerns global capture fisheries production and was constructed from the indicator ER.FSH.CAPT.MT (Capture fisheries production, metric tons), which measures the total volume of fish catches landed for commercial, industrial, recreational, and subsistence purposes (World Bank, 2024).

The data were obtained through the World Bank portal, which integrates information provided by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). The series is already provided at the global level and covers the period 1960–2022, for a total of 63 annual observations. The data are distributed under a CC BY 4.0 license.

Data cleaning and verification were carried out using Microsoft Excel, which was also used for an initial exploratory analysis of the full time series and for the calculation of descriptive statistics (see the attached data file).

Subsequent analyses, including the estimation of the linear model and the identification of structural breaks, were performed using custom Python scripts developed by the author.

The structural break analysis was conducted using the Bai–Perron procedure, which allows for the estimation of one or more breakpoints in a linear regression model (Bai & Perron, 1998, 2003).

A linear model of the following form was specified:

$$Y_t = \alpha + \beta \cdot \text{Year}_t + \varepsilon_t$$

allowing a maximum of two structural breaks (max breaks = 2), corresponding to a maximum of three temporal segments. To avoid excessive fragmentation of the series, the minimum segment length was set at 10 observations in the main specification.

The optimal number of breakpoints was selected using the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), while the significance of the breaks was assessed through sequential F-tests, interpreted with caution in the presence of residual autocorrelation. The F-tests were computed using the standard F distribution and should therefore be regarded as approximations to the specific critical values of the original Bai–Perron procedure (Bai & Perron, 1998, 2003).

The breaks identified in the main specification were also subjected to a sensitivity analysis, replicating the procedure with a minimum segment length of 3 observations in order to verify their stability.

The decision to limit the maximum number of breakpoints to two was made in accordance with the descriptive aim of the study, namely to identify possible long-term transitions in the dynamics of global capture fisheries production without introducing an excessively fine segmentation of the series.

Results

The global capture fisheries production series covers the period 1960–2022 and includes 63 annual observations (Figure 1). Over the full interval, mean production was 73,616,867.37 tonnes, with a median of 78,086,506.13 tonnes and a standard deviation of 19,668,952.88 tonnes, indicating considerable variability over the decades. Observed values ranged from a minimum of 31,603,820.01 tonnes to a maximum of 96,877,060 tonnes, for an overall range of 65,273,239.99 tonnes. The distribution showed slight negative skewness (-0.495) and negative kurtosis (-1.234), suggesting a relatively flat distribution and a slight skew toward higher values. The 95% confidence interval around the mean was 4,953,561.64 tonnes.

The linear regression estimated for the full series revealed a marked upward trend, with a slope coefficient of 997,732.49 tonnes per year and an R^2 of 0.8646, indicating that a substantial share of the overall variability was associated with time (Figure 1). However, this aggregated representation tended to obscure important changes in the internal dynamics of the series.

The structural break analysis conducted using the Bai–Perron procedure, with a maximum of two breakpoints and a minimum segment length of 10 observations, identified two breakpoints located in 1972 and 1992 (Figure 2). According to the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), the three-segment model represented the optimal specification. Compared with the global linear model, the segmented model reduced the residual sum of squares by approximately 90.4%, indicating a substantial improvement in model fit.

The first segment, covering 1960–1971, was characterized by very rapid growth, with a slope of approximately +2.25 million tonnes per year and high explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.975$). The second segment, spanning 1972–1991, still showed significant growth, but at a lower rate, with a slope of approximately +1.54 million tonnes per year ($R^2 = 0.940$), indicating a slowdown relative to the previous phase.

In the third segment (1992–2022), the dynamics changed sharply and structurally: the slope declined dramatically to approximately +30,684 tonnes per year and was not statistically significant ($p = 0.557$), while R^2 dropped to 0.012. This indicates the absence of a relevant linear trend and a substantial stabilization of global production, which fluctuated around a relatively constant level. The mean production for the period 1992–2022 was 91,231,747 tonnes per year.

To assess the stability of the results with respect to model specification, the analysis was replicated using a minimum segment length of 3 observations. Under this more permissive configuration, the estimated breakpoints remained unchanged (1972 and 1992), confirming the robustness of the identified structure. Diagnostic analysis of the global model also showed the presence of residual autocorrelation, which further supports the use of models with structural breaks.

Figure 1. Time series of global capture fisheries production (tonnes, FAO data, 1960–2022). The dashed red line represents the 2-period moving average.

Structural Break Analysis – Results

Figure 2. Structural break analysis of global capture fisheries production (1960–2022) using the Bai–Perron procedure. The upper left panel shows the global linear model. The upper right panel shows the segmented model with two breakpoints (1972 and 1992) and a minimum segment length of 10 observations. The lower left panel displays the residuals of the segmented model, and the lower right panel shows the comparison between observed and fitted values. The segmented model highlights the transition from a growth phase to a phase of substantial stabilization.

Discussion

The analysis of the time series of global capture fisheries production based on FAO-derived data shows that the 1960–2022 trajectory cannot be adequately described by a single linear trend. Although the global regression indicates a positive average growth, the structural break analysis identifies two breakpoints, in 1972 and 1992, which divide the series into three distinct phases: an initial phase of rapid expansion, a subsequent phase of slower growth, and a final phase of substantial stabilization. This result is consistent with the view that capture fisheries systems, both at global and regional scales, do not evolve linearly, but through regime shifts driven by ecological, economic, and institutional factors (Kooiman & Bavinck, 2005; Costello & Ovando, 2019; Costello et al., 2016).

The 1960–1971 segment shows the most intense growth. The 1972–1991 period remains characterized by a positive trend, although at a lower rate. From 1992 to 2022, however, the slope becomes very small and not statistically significant, indicating that global production no longer follows a persistent growth trajectory but fluctuates around a relatively stable level of catches. For

this reason, the 1992 breakpoint represents the main turning point, marking the transition from a growth regime to a regime of stabilization. This pattern is consistent with evidence suggesting that a substantial proportion of global fish stocks is currently exploited at or beyond sustainable levels, limiting the potential for further increases in production (Costello et al., 2016; Froese et al., 2012).

The comparison between the global linear model and the segmented model further supports this interpretation, as the strong reduction in the residual sum of squares indicates that the identified breakpoints capture real changes in the dynamics of the series. Moreover, the results appear robust, as the breakpoints remain unchanged in a sensitivity analysis with a more permissive minimum segment length. In this sense, structural break analysis proves to be an effective tool for detecting regime shifts in complex systems such as fisheries, where nonlinear dynamics and ecological thresholds may play a significant role (Brander, 2007).

This configuration can be interpreted as the combined result of biological constraints, anthropogenic pressures, and global and regional environmental changes, which together define the limits within which global fisheries currently operate (Sainsbury et al., 2018; West et al., 2019).

Conclusions and Limitations

The analysis shows that global capture fisheries production does not follow a single continuous linear trend, but is instead characterized by three distinct phases: a phase of rapid expansion (1960–1971), a phase of slower growth (1972–1991), and a phase of substantial stabilization from 1992 onwards. The breakpoint identified in 1992 represents the most relevant turning point, marking the transition from a growth dynamic to a plateau regime.

The segmented model provides a more accurate description of the series than the global linear regression, showing that overall growth results from the combination of different regimes. The stability of the breakpoints across sensitivity analyses further strengthens the robustness of the results.

Among the limitations, it should be noted that the analysis is based on aggregated global data and does not allow for the identification of regional dynamics. In addition, the presence of residual autocorrelation suggests caution in the interpretation of linear models. Finally, the sequential F-tests were computed using the standard F distribution implemented in the analysis code and should therefore be considered as approximations to the specific critical values of the Bai–Perron procedure.

Author Contributions

The author conceived the study, carried out the data analysis, and wrote the manuscript. GPT-based tools (ChatGPT, OpenAI) were used for exploratory activities, formal improvement of the bibliography, statistical checking, and translation of the manuscript into English.

Data Availability

The data analysed in the present study are available in the attached file: *Pesca World FAO.xlsx*.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest.

Funding

This work received no public or private funding.

References

- Bai, J., & Perron, P. (1998). Estimating and testing linear models with multiple structural changes. *Econometrica*, 66(1), 47–78.
- Bai, J., & Perron, P. (2003). Computation and analysis of multiple structural change models. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 18(1), 1–22.
- Brander, K. M. (2007). Global fish production and climate change. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104(50), 19709–19714.
- Cardinaals, R. P. M., Simon, W. J., Ziegler, F., Wiegertjes, G. F., van der Meer, J., & van Zanten, H. H. E. (2023). Nutrient yields from global capture fisheries could be sustainably doubled through improved utilization and management. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 4, 370. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-023-01024-9>
- Chuenpagdee, R., Degnbol, P., Bavinck, M., Jentoft, S., Johnson, D., Pullin, R., & Williams, S. (2005). Challenges and concerns in capture fisheries and aquaculture. In J. Kooiman, M. Bavinck, S. Jentoft, & R. Pullin (Eds.), *Fish for Life: Interactive Governance for Fisheries* (pp. 25–37). Amsterdam University Press.
- Costello, C., Ovando, D., Hilborn, R., Gaines, S. D., Deschenes, O., & Lester, S. E. (2016). *Global fishery prospects under contrasting management regimes*. *Nature*, 534, 317–320. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature17177>
- Costello, C., & Ovando, D. (2019). Status, institutions, and prospects for global capture fisheries. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 44, 177–200. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-101718-033310>
- Froese, R., Zeller, D., Kleisner, K., & Pauly, D. (2012). What catch data can tell us about the status of global fisheries. *Marine Biology*, 159(6), 1283–1292. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-012-1909-6>
- Kooiman, J., & Bavinck, M. (2005). The governance perspective. In J. Kooiman, M. Bavinck, S. Jentoft, & R. Pullin (Eds.), *Fish for Life: Interactive Governance for Fisheries* (pp. 11–24). Amsterdam University Press.

- Sainsbury, N. C., Genner, M. J., Saville, G. R., Pinnegar, J. K., O'Neill, C. K., Simpson, S. D., & Turner, R. A. (2018). Changing storminess and global capture fisheries. *Nature Climate Change*, 8(8), 655–659. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-018-0206-x>
- West, C. D., Hobbs, E., Croft, S. A., Green, J. M. H., Schmidt, S. Y., & Wood, R. (2019). Improving consumption based accounting for global capture fisheries. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 219, 337–349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.11.298>
- World Bank (2024). *Capture fisheries production (metric tons) (ER.FSH.CAPT.MT)*. Data from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/ER.FSH.CAPT.MT> (Accessed: 3 April 2026).